

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in South Africa is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in South Africa: An Introduction

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In South Africa, both representative and participatory forms of democracy are protected at all levels of government. With respect to representative democracy at the local level, local communities have a constitutional right to elect members of municipal councils.¹⁴⁷ Participatory democracy is emphasized in South Africa's system of local governance and is aimed at ensuring accountability, responsiveness and openness.¹⁴⁸ One of the core constitutional objectives for the establishment of local government is to encourage the involvement of communities and community organisations in matters of local governance (Section 152(1)(e) of the Constitution). Municipal governments are therefore required to develop a governance culture that accommodates both representative and participatory democracy.¹⁴⁹

With respect to participatory democracy, municipalities have a duty to consult and are required to create conditions for and encourage the involvement of the local community¹⁵⁰ in decision-making regarding the level, quality, range and impact of municipal services as well as the available options for service delivery.¹⁵¹ To further this, local communities are allowed to take part in: the preparation, implementation and review of municipal integrated development plans (IDPs); strategic decisions relating to the provision of municipal services; the preparation of municipal budgets; the establishment, implementation and review of municipal performance management systems as well as in monitoring and reviewing municipal performance, including the outcomes and impact of such performance.¹⁵²

Additionally, municipal administrations are under an obligation to provide full and accurate information to the local community regarding the level and standard of municipal services they

¹⁴⁷ Sec 157 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (Constitution) as read with Secs 22 and 23 of the Local Government Municipal Structures Act, 1998.

¹⁴⁸ See the concurring judgment of Sachs J in *Doctors for Life International v Speaker of the National Assembly and Others* (CCT12/05) [2006] ZACC 11; 2006 (12) BCLR 1399 (CC); 2006 (6) SA 416 (CC) 120 [230].

¹⁴⁹ Sec 16, Local Government Municipal Systems Act (Systems Act).

¹⁵⁰ The Municipal Systems Act (Sec 1) defines a local community as comprising: the residents of the municipality; the ratepayers of the municipality; any civic organisations and non-governmental, private sector or labour organisations or bodies which are involved in local affairs within the municipality; as well as visitors and other people residing outside the municipality who, because of their presence in the municipality, make use of services or facilities provided by the municipality. The act lays special emphasis on the poor and other disadvantaged sections of this body of persons.

¹⁵¹ Sec 4(2) as read with Sec 16 of the Systems Act.

¹⁵² Sec 16(1)(a), Systems Act.

are entitled to receive, the costs involved, their rights and duties as well as the available mechanisms of community participation.¹⁵³ Moreover, members of the local community have the right to be informed of decisions taken by the political structures at the local level, which may affect their rights, property and reasonable expectations.¹⁵⁴

To discharge the above obligation, municipalities are required to establish appropriate mechanisms, processes and procedures to enable the local community to participate in the affairs of the municipality.¹⁵⁵ In this respect, municipalities are allowed to establish subcouncils¹⁵⁶ and ward committees¹⁵⁷ which serve as the main participatory structures at the local level.¹⁵⁸ Also, communications done by municipalities to the local community are required to be done through local or regional newspapers or radio broadcast covering the area of the municipality.¹⁵⁹ Additionally, municipalities are required to establish their own official websites (if affordable) or otherwise provide information for display on an organised local government website sponsored or facilitated by the National Treasury.¹⁶⁰

In facilitating participation, municipalities are required to take into account the special needs of people who cannot read or write, people with disabilities, women and other disadvantaged groups.¹⁶¹ When communicating to the local community, municipalities are obligated to take into account language preferences and usage in the municipality as well as other special needs of people who cannot read or write. The Guidelines for Implementing Multilingualism in Local Government issued by the Department of Provincial and Local Government (now called the Department for Cooperative Government and Traditional Affairs) encourage municipal councils, through ward committees to consult local communities in the preparation of a municipal language policy that is then used for purposes of ensuring community

¹⁵³ Sec 6(2)(e) and (f) as read with secs 18 and 95 of the Systems Act.

¹⁵⁴ Sec 5(1), Systems Act.

¹⁵⁵ Sec 17(2), Systems Act.

¹⁵⁶ Subcouncils are made up of those elected councillors representing the wards that constitute the designated area of the municipality as well as an additional number of councillors elected to the municipal council by way of party lists. The latter are appointed by political parties according to their representation in the municipal council. See Sec 63 as read with Schedule 4 of the Municipal Structures Act.

¹⁵⁷ A ward committee is made up of the councillor representing the specific ward and an additional number of not more than ten persons. The latter are elected in accordance with rules laid down by the municipal council and which are aimed at ensuring gender equity as well as the representation of the ward's diverse interests. See Sec 73 of the Municipal Structures Act.

¹⁵⁸ Sec 7 (d) and (e), Structures Act; Nico Steytler and Jaap De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2016) 6-12(3) – 6-13.

¹⁵⁹ Sec 21 (1), Systems Act.

¹⁶⁰ Sec 21B, Systems Act.

¹⁶¹ Sec 17(3), Systems Act.

participation.¹⁶² This is key in facilitating participation in both rural and urban local governments.

To participate, members of the local community have the right to submit written or oral recommendations, representations and complaints to the political structures at the local government level and to receive prompt responses to them.¹⁶³ Municipalities are in return required to provide for: the receipt, processing and consideration of petitions and complaints; notification and public comment procedures; public meetings and hearings by municipal councils and other local political structures; consultative processes with locally recognised community organisations as well as traditional authorities and to also make provision for forums to report back to the local communities.¹⁶⁴ Additionally, the meetings of a municipal council on the municipality's annual report are required to be open to the public and reasonable time allowed for members of the local community to address the council and for the discussion of any written submissions received from the local community.¹⁶⁵

To ensure local participatory processes are undertaken, municipalities are required, when submitting a copy of their adopted IDP to the provincial government, to provide a summary of the process followed and a statement that the required process, which includes community participation, has been complied with (also see WP4 on IDP).¹⁶⁶ Where this has not been done, the provincial government is mandated to request the relevant municipal council to comply with the required process and make consequential adjustments to the IDP.¹⁶⁷ However, in practice, this constitutes a weak form of oversight given that the provincial government mainly focuses on alignment with intergovernmental relations issues and less on public participation.

This has given room for a more robust role by the courts in ensuring reasonable public participation through judicial review. In instances where there are allegations of a failure of public involvement, the Constitutional Court in *Doctors for Life International v Speaker of the National Assembly and Others*¹⁶⁸ developed a reasonableness test to be applied in determining whether the degree of involvement met the Constitutional requirement for participation.¹⁶⁹ The test outlines a set of general factors for consideration which include: the nature and importance of the decision; efficiency of decision-making in terms of time and expense; intensity of the decision's impact on the public and whether there was any urgency that informed the decision. Whereas this standard was developed in light of involvement with Parliament and provincial legislatures, Steytler and De Visser argue that 'a municipality's efforts

¹⁶² Leah Cohen, 'Guidelines of Multilingualism in Local Government: Ambitious Rhetoric or a Realisable Goal?' (2008) 10 Local Government Bulletin.

¹⁶³ Sec 5(1), Systems Act.

¹⁶⁴ Sec 17(2), Systems Act.

¹⁶⁵ Sec 130, Local Government Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA).

¹⁶⁶ Sec 32(1)(a) and (b), Systems Act.

¹⁶⁷ Sec 32(2), Systems Act.

¹⁶⁸ (CCT12/05) [2006] ZACC 11; 2006 (12) BCLR 1399 (CC); 2006 (6) SA 416 (CC) 120.

¹⁶⁹ Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 6-16.

at involving the local community must meet the same standard of reasonableness.¹⁷⁰ Subsequent court decisions such as the case of *Borbet South Africa (Pty) Ltd and Others v Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality*¹⁷¹ have actually held that the standard is even higher for municipalities.

Additionally, the courts have been liberal with the question of standing such as to allow community members and community organisations the right to initiate proceedings against local governments on questions of public participation.¹⁷² This was the approach adopted by the court in *Stellenbosch Ratepayers' Association v Stellenbosch Municipality*¹⁷³ as well as in *Mnquma Local Municipality and Another v The Premier of the Eastern Cape and Others*.¹⁷⁴ The courts in both cases adopted a broad approach to standing to allow a ratepayers' association and members of the community respectively to bring cases contesting subnational decisions on the basis of want of public participation.¹⁷⁵

To facilitate participatory democracy at the local government level, municipalities are allowed to use their resources and to annually allocate funds in their budgets for purposes of ensuring community participation.¹⁷⁶

When making regulations or issuing guidelines regarding community participation at the local government level, the minister for local government is required to differentiate between different kinds of municipalities according to their respective capacities to comply with the statutory provisions for public participation¹⁷⁷ including making provision for phased application of public participation requirements that have a financial or administrative burden.¹⁷⁸ While this was key in ensuring the accommodation of both urban and rural municipalities by allowing them to undertake participatory processes with due regard to their respective capacities, the provisions are currently equally applicable to all municipalities.¹⁷⁹

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996

¹⁷⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁷¹ (3751/2011) [2014] ZAECPEHC 35; 2014 (5) SA 256 (ECP) (The Borbet Case).

¹⁷² Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 6-7.

¹⁷³ [2009] JOL 24616 (WCC) [17].

¹⁷⁴ (231/2009) [2009] ZAECBHC 14 (5 August 2009).

¹⁷⁵ Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 6-7.

¹⁷⁶ Sec 16, Systems Act.

¹⁷⁷ Sec 22(2)(a), Systems Act.

¹⁷⁸ Sec 22, Systems Act.

¹⁷⁹ Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 6-20.

Local Government: Municipal Structures Act 117 of 1998

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Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act 56 of 2003

Borbet South Africa (Pty) Ltd and Others v Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality (3751/2011) [2014] ZAECPEHC 35; 2014 (5) SA 256 (ECP)

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Steytler N and De Visser J, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2016)

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

